

PROFIT-AND-LOSS SHARING THROUGH IMPACT INVESTMENT FUNDS: POSSIBILITY FOR BREAKING THE INVISIBLE CEILING WITH MUSLIM IMMIGRANT ENTREPRENEURS IN NORWAY

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Abstract

This paper examines the challenge of financial inclusion for Muslim Immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway. Based on a larger project of the Norwegian Research Council-Funded Project with a dataset of over 65 interviews and qualitative data collections, as well as a literature review and desk study, the paper takes the approach that an Islamic proscription against interest-based financing leads to financial exclusion for Muslim entrepreneurs in Norway, where Islamic finance tools are not offered. Research reveals that Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs are unable to access acceptable financial tools formally, and instead rely on informal avenues for financing that limit their growth potential and impede integration. The paper argues that developing and amplifying a profit-and-loss sharing financing framework through impact investment funds is one way to overcome these challenges. The paper concludes that this is of importance because the successful financial integration of immigrant entrepreneurs increases equality, labor market integration, and access to healthy workplaces, which are important aims in the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: entrepreneurialism; Islamic finance; ethical finance; impact investment funds; integration; Norway

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INTRODUCTION

Mohammed, a 35-year-old Syrian refugee, arrived in Oslo in 2013. He worked hard to open a small grocery store with his brother and mother, using informal financing from the local mosque. The small business is doing well, but he would like to expand the business to improve his family’s living conditions and would also like to help his sister open a cafe or restaurant. Mohammed said that he would especially like the opportunity to employ other Muslim immigrants in Norway because “it can be really difficult for them to find jobs while they learn Norwegian and get settled in their new lives becoming Norwegian citizens.” However, Mohammed is reluctant to

take out a formal business loan because the interest charges (*riba*) are forbidden in Islam. He approached his local mosque for assistance, but so far there have not been any feasible financing alternatives. Mohammed has hit the “invisible ceiling” of financial exclusion that prevents Muslim entrepreneurs of micro- and small-sized businesses from growing their enterprises in Norway. Like other Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway, Mohammed feels financially excluded from growing his business and improving his living conditions and working life. He is therefore unable to contribute to the greater business community and institutions. He experiences inequalities in his integration in Norway and obstacles to fully realizing his active citizenship: “integreiring gjennom jobb (integration through job).”

Since the financial crisis of 2008, Norway has seen roughly 6,000 to 9,000 new firms established annually (Fjærli, Iancu, & Raknerud, 2013). Norway supports a strong entrepreneurial culture for small businesses through a three-pronged approach: increasing 1) access to capital at an early stage, 2) access to competence, and 3) a business-friendly environment (Norwegian Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, 2020). And it has experienced some success: there are more entrepreneurs per capita in Norway than in the USA (Chafkin, 2011). However, there is much room for improvement: these Norwegian firms are overwhelmingly micro-enterprises, most with three or fewer employees, and with a 10-year firm survival rate of 50%-60%. Norway’s efforts to promote entrepreneurship amongst immigrant populations only began in 2003, and 14% of entrepreneurs are immigrants or children of immigrants (Vinogradov, 2008).

Existing literature demonstrates that financial exclusion amongst entrepreneurs in Norway takes place because the sector fails to recognize their unique needs - as immigrants, religious congregants, according to gender, amongst other needs (Brekke, 2018, Brekke and Larsen, 2020; Lin, 2011; Ljunngren & Alsos, 2006). Specifically, religious concerns about interest-based financing (described below) prevent Muslim populations from engaging in debt-based business activities and restrict their ability to receive formal funding for their projects. Islamic financial development in Muslim-majority countries has advanced in recent decades (Jan & Asutay, 2019; Tobin, 2020b). However, most Muslim-minority countries have not developed the necessary Islamic structures to respond to the financial aspirations of the Muslim immigrant communities to help them overcome financial exclusion (Tameme & Asutay, 2012; Asutay, 2013). Most Muslim entrepreneurs in Norway depend upon mosque support, investors’ personal savings, or interest-free loans from family and friends, and this dependency severely constrains growth potential (Brekke, 2018; Brekke et.al.,2019). Importantly, the amount of financing available for these entrepreneurs is limited.

These limitations also inhibit Muslim immigrant integration in Norway, as they lack financial opportunities to become equal stakeholders in society, contribute to the development of their communities, and create value in their new country. While the UK, for example, has demonstrated a certain level of access for Islamic financial opportunities for its Muslim communities through necessary regulative and legal changes (Tameme & Asutay, 2012), Norway has not developed such structures and institutionalization. Therefore, there have been delays in Muslim communities

becoming part of economic value creation and being more fully integrated into Norwegian society as community stakeholders (Lin, 2011).

This paper explores some central aspects of Islamic financing models and formulates an explorative solution in the profit-and-loss sharing form of social impact investment funding. The incorporation of both social and financial concerns into a “doubled bottom line” addresses the questions of ethical finance by both answering entrepreneurs’ individual concerns and larger societal needs with regards to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

BACKGROUND: ISLAMIC PROSCRIPTIONS FOR PROFIT-AND-LOSS SHARING (PLS) AND MUSLIM IMMIGRANT ENTREPRENEURIAL NEEDS IN NORWAY

Since the late 1980s, widespread consensus has emerged on one of Islamic finance’s basic contractual and technical principles, the Qur’anic injunction against *riba*, which translates literally as “increase” but is most frequently understood as “interest.” It is interpreted widely as a universal prohibition against both usurious and non-usurious rates of interest (Asutay, 2013, Brekke, 2018, Tobin, 2016a). One way that these challenges of debt-based financing can be overcome is through a profit-and-loss sharing arrangement (PLS) in an impact investment fund (IIF). This injunction against interest has resulted in two primary forms of banking and financial services, which are variations of PLS endorsed in Islam.

First is *mudaraba*, which is essentially venture capitalism: investor(s) entrust an entrepreneur with capital, who then undertakes a particular enterprise, sharing the profits with the investors; one partner contributes capital in the form of money and the other contributes only her/his business skills and services. This is the model that the Prophet Mohammed and his first wife, Khadija, are said to have exemplified in their joint commercial enterprises. *Musharaka*, the second form, is similar to *mudaraba*. However, in this second form the entrepreneur also exposes her own capital for both profit and loss, rather than solely the capital of the financier; it is the participation of two or more parties in a contracted business venture with defined amounts of capital for jointly carrying out a business and for sharing profit and loss in specified proportions. This second model is based upon the relationship established between Muslim immigrants from Mecca and locals in Medina, in which the two groups shared work and outcomes for an integrated life together. Within the contemporary Islamic finance industry, these two PLS methods constitute major contractual arrangements, generate innovative entrepreneurial ventures, and hold out great promise for Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway.

The very few studies of Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway reveal a tremendous need for Islamically-compliant financing in PLS (Brekke, 2018; Brekke and Larsen, 2020). These studies show that more than 60% of surveyed Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs strongly agreed that interest is forbidden in Islam, and 78% said that they would become customers of an Islamic bank if given the option. The sentiments were shared by the 2,000+ non-entrepreneur survey respondents at similar rates. The research was also revealing for its qualitative contributions, which

demonstrated that not only were Muslim entrepreneurs concerned about their own religious piety as it related to conventional finance, but also for the reputational risk that they would undertake by utilizing conventional finance. In other words, Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs were interested in an Islamic financial alternative because they believed it would be well-received in the community and promote integration and goodwill. The literature bears out that Islamic financial alternatives for Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs are real solutions for positive socio-economic outcomes in Norway (Brekke, 2020).

Beyond religion, gender is also an important consideration. Norway is well-known for gender equity. According to the 2020 Global Gender Gap Index Rating Report, Norway ranked second in the Gender Parity chart. Nonetheless, economics, finance, and business persist as male-dominated spheres here. According to their website, the NHH graduated 18 male PhDs and 14 females in 2017-8. 80% of entrepreneurs in Norway are male (Fjærli, Iancu, & Raknerud, 2013). One statistic suggests the picture may not be so simple or well defined: immigrant women to Norway are entrepreneurs at higher rates than their non-immigrant counterparts (Fjærli, Iancu, & Raknerud, 2013). Does this also hold true for female Muslim immigrants to Norway? We simply do not know. The picture is made even more complex by the great strides that Muslim women have achieved in Norway towards gender equality: women often enjoy much more gender-equality in their everyday lives than stereotypes suggest, with young Muslim women living more “liberally” than their parents (Nyhagen, 2004). The experiences of female Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs thus merit deeper investigation.

We know that Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs world-wide have pursued alternative Islamic funding mechanisms in the absence of formal Islamic financing, including rotating credit and saving circles, and Postal Savings (Tobin, 2016a, 2017). We know very little about how mosque congregations and leaders facilitate business contacts and networks (Brekke et. al., 2019) and need to understand how Islamic legal and moral authority concerning finance and business is communicated through different channels (cf. Bang, 2011, 2021). Some studies find that religious congregations serve as important sources of economic and social capital for entrepreneurs, across different cultural milieus (Brekke et. al., 2019). As Brekke and Larsen (2020) demonstrates, a key concern among at least some Muslim entrepreneurs in the Nordic countries is about access to Islamic finance, and his work demonstrates that Muslim entrepreneurs lack access to formal funding mechanisms consistent with their religious views. This creates the “invisible ceiling” we reference early on that, in the words of informants, prevents them from expanding their businesses.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORY

To underscore the role and possibility of PLS in IIF, we employ the theory of moral economies, which conceptualizes the economy as a location for normative moral action: economies are—or at least ought to be—based on goodness, fairness, and justice, and not on a “free hand” operating independently of such concerns.

Theoretically spearheaded by James Scott (1977), the moral economy literature on immigrant entrepreneurship emerged in the 1970s and 1980s as researchers explored the emergence of “ethnic enterprises.” Some of the more recent research theorizing ethnic entrepreneurship looks more specifically at the role of religion as an Islamic moral economy (see, for example: Asutay 2013, Hasan & Asutay 2014, Izhar & Asutay 2020, Asutay & Turkistani 2015, Asutay & Marzban 2015, Jan & Asutay 2019, Mergaliev, Asutay, Avdukic & Karbhari 2020; Bang 2011; Brekke 2018; Norbakk 2020; Tobin 2011, 2013, 2014, 2016a, 2019, 2020a). Frequently the Islamic moral economy literature points to compatibilities between Islam and capitalism, demonstrated by the Prophet Mohammed. As the model Islamic entrepreneur, with financing from his first wife, Khadija, the Prophet sold goods in Syria and returned to Khadija the principal payment and the agreed-upon profit. The model solidifies moral-economic compatibilities, PLS possibilities and ethical standards, and endorses gendered entrepreneurialism as well. Female Muslim entrepreneurs have responded to the example of Khadija by becoming self-employed, establishing businesses and organizations working for social change, both historically and currently. And these religious frameworks have moved with Muslim migration (Asutay, 2013): European Muslims’ demand for financing that correspond with Islamic values creates business and transnational networks based Muslim identities in the marketplace.

However, it is important to recognize that religion does not determine economic behaviour (Tobin, 2016a). The effect of religion on entrepreneurship is highly dependent on context, which includes both the financial environment and political and social realities. This is the primary finding in Dodd & Gotsis’ review of the literature that addresses the interrelationship between religion and entrepreneurship (2007). They also find that entrepreneurs with high religious adherence tend to use religious criteria to inform decision making, even at the expense of short-term commercial interests. Even long after the influence of Max Weber’s *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, the literature that explores the influences of spirituality and religiosity on entrepreneurship concludes that there is “a rich connection between the personal values of religion and spirituality in the life of the entrepreneur and the success of their venture” (Dodd & Gotsis 2007).

In 1975 immigration laws restricted unskilled worker immigration, but enabled family reunification, education migrants (student visas), and skilled worker employment that brought in a large-number of typically well-educated immigrants that continues today (Lin 2011). Beyond this, refugees and asylum seekers have increased in recent years, with populations from Asia, Africa, the Americas, and Turkey constituting the largest percentage of immigrants. These populations also constitute the largest share of entrepreneurs: more than 44% of small shops in Oslo are “ethnic shops;” the service and food sectors are more than 50% immigrant-run; and more than 17% of immigrants become entrepreneurs (Lin, 2011). The primary supposition for this dynamic is the blocked mobility hypothesis, which states that immigrants are pushed into entrepreneurship because of structural barriers in the labour market that prevent their ability to compete on equal terms with natives (Vinogradov, 2008). The barriers may be formal discrimination such as “natives-first” hiring, or informal such as native-language policies or a lack of recognition of

foreign education and credentials. It occurs in nearly every Western country with a nearly universal outcome: immigrants become entrepreneurs at higher rates than natives (Trevizo & Lopez, 2018).

This underpins some urgency: the government, private sector, and social communities have a pressing need to understand and nurture the positive socio-economic outcomes of a larger entrepreneurial base, however venture capitalism for or non-debt financed small- and micro-enterprises are not the first industry go-to due to limited returns and high risk. This is despite the fact that the small- and micro-enterprises are socially quite promising. Entrepreneurialism is one way that socio-economic equality, healthy workplaces, financial inclusion, and immigrant integration occur. It is a potent mechanism for cultivating social and cultural capital and integrating immigrants (Aldrich & Waldinger, 1990), especially as it can create local “heroes” and valorise the social role of immigrant entrepreneurs for young people (Wolfensberger, 1972).

THE OBSTACLES AND PROMISES OF PLS AND IIFS IN NORWAY

While resistance to promoting PLS alternatives in Norway may have some prejudicial linkages to immigration policy and outcomes more generally, as described above, a more immediate reason for resistance to PLS may be the challenge of obtaining and utilizing venture capital funds for micro-enterprises. As Langeland (2006) discusses, in Norway a lack of competent capital at the early development stage (e.g. moving from micro- to medium-sized enterprises) is a serious obstacle for financing innovation amongst Muslim and non-Muslim entrepreneurs alike. Further, venture capitalists, who would be necessary in the Islamic *mudaraba* arrangements discussed above, invest mainly in high-technology industries and primarily in enterprises which have a growth potential in international markets. Venture capital investments tend to be geographically clustered in urban areas, and large cities have lower transaction costs and higher potential for human capital investments, information technology support, and other innovation advantages.

The Islamic *mudaraba* arrangement also acknowledges that venture capital endeavors require more than capital to develop. The theory of moral economies shares the perspective that ethical principles of business administration and industrial knowledge coexist with business acumen, know-how, and technical competence. Some have contended that such strategic activities in venture capitalism are “actually their most important contribution to portfolio enterprises’ results” (Langeland 2006; Wijbenga et al., 2003). Venture capital is or at least should be therefore “more than money since it ensures that the enterprises get business administration experience and strategic consultancy services, as well as giving them access to financial and industrial networks” (Bygrave & Timmons, 1992; Langeland 2006).

Langeland’s study (2006) found that the Norwegian venture capital industry is “young and fairly immature.” The first venture capital firm was started in the early 1980s, but most venture capital activity in Norway is from the late 1990s. The

limited partnership model is the dominant form in Norway, and clusters overwhelmingly in cities where venture capital firms prefer “lower risk investments, improved rates of return, and add value to new ventures” (Langeland, 2006). The study finds that even regional public venture capital funds “prefer to invest within a narrower geographic scope than other venture capital firms” (Langeland, 2006).

Norway is a low-population density country with Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs residing throughout smaller cities and towns and in rural areas. Given Langeland’s findings on the importance of geographic and urban clustering as well as narrow industry diversity as strong preferences by venture capital firms, venture capital in the Islamic *mudaraba* arrangement alone as it currently stands is unlikely to assist Norway’s Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs.

However, one work around may be to turn to an Impact Investment Fund (or “Social Impact Investment Fund;” Here: IIF). In one model, IIFs effectively serve as a type of venture capital in the form of venture philanthropy. IIFs are those investments that explicitly aim to achieve “more than capital” returns or increase profit margins. They “intentionally target specific social objectives along with a financial return and measure the achievement of both” (Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014). They can build new markets, purchase specific social outcomes, and serve as a market steward. And IIFs are growing: as of 2014, \$45 trillion US dollars are in mainstream investment funds that have “publicly committed to incorporate environmental, social and governance factors into their investment decisions” (Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014). Some IIFs specifically work to target impact on the SDGs; or priorities aligned with those (see NBIM Responsible investment www.nbim.no for a publicly-aligned investment fund, or Ferd <https://ferd.no/baerekraft/hva-er-impact-investing/>; for a private one). As we discuss below, an expansion of such a financing model could serve to achieve multiple SDGs, including the umbrella focus of financial inclusion for Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway.

An IIF is a combination of capital supply and social interest, capital demand by an impact-driven industry partner, and connecting intermediaries (Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014). The 5 principal components of IIFs include (Social Impact Investment Taskforce, 2014):

1. Impact-seeking purchasers – these provide the sources of revenue that underpin investment in impact-driven organizations. Such purchasers can include governments, consumers, corporations or foundations.
2. Impact-driven organizations – all types of organizations which have a long-term social mission, set outcome objectives and measure their achievement, whether they be social sector organizations or impact-driven businesses.
3. Forms of finance – which are needed to address a range of different investment requirements.
4. Channels of impact capital – to connect investors to impact-driven organizations in situations where the sources of impact capital do not invest directly in impact-driven organizations.
5. Sources of impact capital – to provide the investment flows needed.

IIFs are particularly well-suited for entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs are often interested in applying their creative energy in ways that address problems of local concerns, as

they may be rooted in their immediate communities in ways that echo those of Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs discussed above. Beyond local environs, IIFs may also help entrepreneurs scale-up ideas and concerns of a national or transnational nature. IIFs also carry tremendous flexibility that make the arrangement more attractive to investors: geographical clustering or industry diversity concerns of venture capitalists in Norway give way to asking key questions about the social impact of a small business in rural Norway, which may not otherwise be captured in financial risk assessments. A targeted focus on regional diversity; as well as thinking of niche-markets also from a social perspective may lead to less clustering and urban bias.

One example can be found in eastern Africa (Coffie, 2013). In a study of 20 entrepreneurs from Kenya and Uganda, the researcher found that socially-inclined businesses play positive roles in poor communities; that long-term capital is important for starting new enterprises; and the success of the social enterprise depends upon the technical assistance inputs. Philanthropic capital in entrepreneurial IIFs had positive effects on creating employment opportunities and increasing access to social services for the community. The study concludes that targeting socially-inclined small- and medium-sized enterprises contributes to social change.

In effect, IIFs could resemble either the Islamic *mudaraba* or *musharaka* arrangements, depending on the capital investment of the entrepreneur. IIFs cohere ethically with the intentions of Islam and moral economies, and they provide for a kind of public-private partnership that can serve interests for both social services and for a funding mechanism. A potential windfall effect of making IIF's accessible and well-known may be increased creativity and interest in social entrepreneurship, simply as it proves to be a more viable business model for immigrant entrepreneurs.

A potential shortcoming in this model may be the explicit focus on social impact, as it would exclude those entrepreneurs who are not necessarily engaging the "double bottom line," that is those who are not engaging in social impact or have the capacity to do the reporting work associated with tracing impact. In addition, the need for "measurable" impact, or "evidence-based" insight, is cumbersome (Engle Merry, 2011), as it tends to a) increase cost and labor related to reporting; and b) in some instances reduces participation to those who contribute to "measurable" impact. In some instances, it can lead to a focus on "instrumental" changes rather than "substantial" ones. This can be the case in "women's participation," where targeting the percentage of women represented in a political organization is easier to measure than say, actual decision-making power (see Tønnessen and Norbakk, 2015). And indeed, there are significant disagreements on how to measure impact, which complicates IIFs (World Economic Forum, 2013). Finance and development (in a broad understanding) can operate on different timescales, which underscores the importance for involvement from state or other public entities in order to ensure sustainability and impact-tracing beyond investment cycles.

As a form of ethical and – for Muslims – morally acceptable form of investment, the IIF model could hold great potential both for entrepreneurs and investors. For Norway's Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs IIFs may be the best workable options in the current regulatory and financial environment.

CONCLUSIONS

Looking at IIFs from a moral economy framework challenges and even inverts the hierarchy of priorities for investors. Social impact becomes an ethical imperative and analyzing it as such could have further theoretical and applied implications. Asutay (2013) points out the moral basis for Islamic banking and finance, and his analytical framework could be further adapted to include IIFs more comprehensively especially in the case of profit-and-loss sharing investments in Muslim-owned businesses.

IIFs for Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway respond to one of the umbrella expectations of the UN-Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically financial inclusion. Financial inclusion is positively associated with poverty alleviation, entrepreneurship development, labour market inclusion, and individual and community development. Therefore, financial inclusion, as a target, through IIFs and entrepreneurship development can help meet seven additional SDGs, including: SDG1 on alleviation poverty; SDG 3 on promoting good health and well-being; SDG 5 on achieving gender equality and economic empowerment of women; SDG 8 on promoting economic growth and jobs; SDG 9 on supporting industry, innovation, and infrastructure; SDG 10 on reducing inequality; and SDG 17 through savings mobilization for investment, which can help with economic growth. Thus, the provision of Islamic finance for entrepreneurial purposes can substantiate the importance of financial inclusion.

The prospects for IIFs in PLS as an Islamic financing mechanism go beyond Muslim and immigrant communities in Norway. They shed light on the contours of challenges and obstacles that hinder all entrepreneurs from growing their enterprises and provides solutions. Enhancing IIFs for Muslim immigrant entrepreneurs in Norway will make the country a leader in the empowerment of immigrant entrepreneurs, unleashing creativity, facilitating integration, and creating value for society. Norway can become a role model in Europe, driving international political and diplomatic goodwill that stretches far beyond the immediate national rewards.

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